

THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF STRENGTHENING THE SOCIAL PROTECTION OF THE POPULATION IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND STATISTICAL INDICATORS IN IT

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Abstract. *The article highlights significant changes in social protection systems, namely programs and laws developed by the state. It examines social assistance programs such as pensions, access to health care, and key aspects of social protection aimed at vulnerable groups of the population, and analyzes their statistical indicators. By analyzing data from national and international sources, the study explains the progress made in social protection reforms in Uzbekistan, including increasing the minimum pension and expanding social security initiatives. The article also highlights issues such as adjusting benefits to inflation and further improving coverage in order to reduce poverty.*

Keywords: *social protection, pension systems, social security, vulnerable groups, poverty reduction, economic stability, access to health care, statistical observations, social security, government reforms, social assistance programs.*

INTRODUCTION. In recent years, Uzbekistan has made significant progress in modernizing its social protection system. Systemic reforms are being implemented to strengthen social protection of the population by expanding the volume and types of social services provided by the state.

According to statistics, the cost of financing social programs has doubled compared to GDP. The coverage of low-income families by beneficiaries has increased fivefold. In addition, new types of benefits have been introduced for people with disabilities and their caregivers.

The relevance of the topic is determined by the following factors:

- The new version of the Constitution proclaims the principles of the welfare state.
- Ensuring state protection of the rights of the elderly, disabled and other socially vulnerable segments of the population.
- Constitutional obligations of the state to promote employment and education of people with disabilities.
- The need to reform the social protection sector based on a unified approach.

The significance of this research work lies in the fact that it serves to implement the objectives set in the following regulatory legal acts:

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 5, 2019 No. UF-5655

Resolution No. PQ-4796 dated August 3, 2020;

Resolution No. PQ-4699 dated April 20, 2020;

Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. VM-841 dated October 20, 2018;

Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dated 06.08.2024 No. 484 "On measures to provide state-guaranteed social services to needy segments of the population" was adopted.

Methodology. The issue of social protection has become increasingly important instrument for protecting the rights and interests of the most vulnerable segments of the population of the state, improving their living conditions and ensuring social justice for them. Uzbekistan, with a youth population of more than 36 million, is implementing important reforms in the area of social protection [1]. The study highlights modern methods of improving the well-being of the population, the experience of Uzbekistan and prospects for the future.

1. In the processes of individualization of social assistance and targeting, assistance should be directed only to the most needy groups to improve the efficiency of the social protection system. To do this:

- Expansion of the "Unified Social Register": fair distribution of assistance by accurately recording income, living conditions and needs of families.

- Covering utility bills for low-income people with preferential subsidies, providing food packages for children and school supplies.

- Special programs for people with disabilities and the elderly: mobile medical services, psychological support centers, employment opportunities for them [2].

2. In the process of investing in the health system, well-being is directly related to the level of health and education.

- In expanding the health network, increasing the number of medical institutions in rural areas, improving the skills of doctors, and introducing preventive programs [3].

This can be illustrated by healthy society is the foundation of a prosperous society, so the effective organization of this process is an important task.

- The main preventive task: implementation of programs to combat drug addiction, obesity and stress among adolescents.

- Modern equipment of rural outpatient clinics within the framework of the program "Further improvement of the health care system" adopted in 2023 for the development of rural medicine.

- When conducting online consultations, it is necessary to introduce the opportunity for residents of remote areas to consult with specialists through the Telemed platform.

3. Education is the main means of social mobility necessary for providing education and vocational training.

- To provide preschool education, create free kindergartens for children from low-income families (for example, Bolajon centers).

- Attracting talented students to study at foreign universities through scholarships and grants (cooperation with the CIS countries).

- Develop a system for organizing advanced training courses for young people in the field of IT, construction, tourism within the framework of the "Blessing for Labor" project in the field of vocational education.

4. In the system of promoting employment and supporting small businesses, increasing the level of family income by reducing unemployment.

- In the process of developing a startup ecosystem, provide grants to young people through IT parks, technology parks and the "Youth is our Future" fund.

- Developing employment opportunities for women through home work (for example, handicrafts, sewing), microloans (loans for women at 1%).

- In regulating labor migration, it is necessary to establish as an important task the improvement of agreements with the International Labor Organization to protect the rights of citizens working abroad.

5. When modernizing infrastructure, developing a system through propaganda: good infrastructure is the key to improving the quality of life:

- Providing villages with clean drinking water through the "Khalkobad" and "Water Supply of Uzbekistan" water supply projects.

- Develop a plan for the construction of about 1 million units of affordable housing in 2021-2025 as part of the "Houses of Uzbekistan" housing program.

- Carrying out work to expand intercity railway and bus lines in the transport network (using the Tashkent-Nukus high-speed train as an example).

6. With the use of digitalization and innovation, technologies increase the speed and openness of social services.

- Citizens can receive online information about all social payments (pensions, pension savings) on the "Personal Account" platform.

- Blockchain technology: tracking the movement of aid funds, preventing corruption.

- Improving artificial intelligence and smart devices for people with disabilities (for example, voice navigators for the blind).

7. The need to use global experience and financial resources to strengthen international cooperation and the need to develop a procedure for their systematic use.

Table 1: International cooperation projects [4]

Organization	Project Title	Amount of money	Result
World Bank	“Modernizing Social Protection”	\$500 million	aid to 1 million families
UN	Sustainable Development Goals (poverty reduction)	\$200 million	500,000 jobs
International Labor Organization (ILO)	To eradicate child labor	\$50 million	30,000 children will return to education

- The UN Sustainable Development Goals are primarily aimed at developing projects to eradicate poverty, improve health care and promote quality education by 2030.

- The Social Protection System Modernization Project worth US\$500 million (2022–2026), financed by World Bank loans.

- The International Labor Organization (ILO) Guidelines for the Elimination of Child Labor and the Improvement of Working Conditions.

8. In the development of the process of strengthening social and family values
 Social well-being is unthinkable without the spiritual stability of society.

- One-time payment for a child over 3 years old for large families in the family policy system, the state program "Family-2024".

- Activation of the neighborhood system: The role of neighborhood guards and social workers in supporting vulnerable families.

- Cultural events: "Healthy Generation" festivals, family sports competitions.

The main goal of the study is to ensure the rights and interests of citizens in social protection, improve the quality of social services provided to the population, and introduce a modern management system based on international standards in this area [5].

Diagram 1. Distribution of assistance to families with many children (This scheme was developed by the author)

Results and discussion. Therefore, the issue of improving the social protection system is of urgent importance for Uzbekistan, and the reforms being carried out in this area will serve the sustainable development of society [6].

The study of income stratification of the population in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the improvement of the social protection system are of urgent importance. Data obtained based on the results of sample household surveys show an uneven distribution of income by 10 percent (decile) groups of the population.

Table 1.
Income distribution by 10 percentile groups of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan [7]

Decile groups	Portion (%)
I Decile	2.8
II Decile	4.1
III Decile	5.2
IV Decile	6.3
V Decile	7.4
VI Decile	8.6
VII Decile	10.0
VIII Decile	11.7
IX Decile	14.2
X Decile	29.7

Source: Compiled based on data from the State Statistics Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

As can be seen from the table, the top 10 percent of the population (decile X) receives 29.7 percent of total income, while the bottom 10 percent (decile I) receives only 2.8 percent. These figures indicate the existence of income inequality in society [8].

In 2022, state budget expenditures on social assistance programs amounted to 0.97 percent of GDP. This indicator is lower than the average regional expenditures of the countries of Europe and Central Asia.

A large part of the population still does not have full social security. Approximately 60 percent of the working population works in the informal sector and does not participate in social insurance programs. This situation indicates the need to further improve the social protection system.

For the effective implementation of the new national strategy for social protection, it is advisable to take the following measures:

- 1. Accurately calculate the necessary financial resources;*
- 2. Determine the available and additional funds needed;*
- 3. Form a factual basis for assessing the impact of the social protection system;*
- 4. Consider optimizing the composition and direction of state spending;*
- 5. Expand budget opportunities in the field of social protection [9].*

Improving the social protection system in Uzbekistan, especially by involving people employed in the informal sector in social insurance programs, will improve the level of social protection of the population.

An important task remains to cover broad sections of society with social protection.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, it can be said that many of the above measures are necessary to improve the effectiveness of the social protection system in Uzbekistan.

This analysis demonstrates that social protection is the responsibility of not only the state, but also of each citizen. Uzbekistan has taken important steps along this path, but sustainable development is a system that needs to be constantly studied. These measures are not official.

In conclusion, it can be said that many of the above measures are necessary to improve the effectiveness of the social protection system in Uzbekistan.

It can be concluded that social protection is the responsibility of not only the state, but also of each citizen. Uzbekistan has taken important steps along this path, but sustainable development is a system that needs to be constantly studied. These measures are not official. It should be implemented in a coordinated manner with the overall efforts aimed at increasing the level of employment.

It can be emphasized that in accordance with the approach of ensuring a minimum level of social protection for the entire population, it is recommended to strengthen social protection (including social insurance, maternity protection, decent working conditions and minimum wage) for persons employed in the informal sector of the national economy by expanding the coverage of social insurance programs. These measures should be implemented in coordination with overall efforts to increase the share of formal employment.

Unemployment benefit recipients account for approximately 1 percent of the total number of registered unemployed. This situation means that unemployment insurance, which is the basis of international social security standards, is practically absent in Uzbekistan.

Therefore, in our opinion, the poverty level of the population and it is necessary to analyze the available statistical indicators of social protection of the population, draw conclusions and make proposals [10].

To analyze existing statistical indicators of social protection of the population, we propose the following qualitative indicators.

- labor productivity;
- activity of business entities;
- employment level;
- level of labor market tension;
- poverty level;
- economic activity index;
- business sentiment index.

The analysis of existing statistical indicators of social protection of the population is an important indicator for an accurate statistical assessment of the poverty level of the population, which is its primary goal.

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